

Table S3. Dual-luciferase report assay vectors

Gene	Vector sequences
Linc00668-WT	5'AGGUGACAUCACAUUUGACAGAGGAAGUUACAAAGGUUAUC AACGCCUCGUCUAGUCUAUUCCCAAGAAGGACAGACAACGAAG UUCAAAGUAAGAGAGAAAUUUGUUUGUUCCAACCGAAGGUA CCAAGGAAGAAUUUCUUAACAACUUCCACACAGAAGUCUAAGUA AAUCACAAGCACCUUGGGGUCCCUUUCGACUACAUUUUUGGAG AAAAAAGAGGGUAUACAGAGUUUUUCAACAUAAAAGACCCAG GUUCCCUAGACGUUCGGAGGAUUUCCGUAAAAGGUAACAGUGAU GGUGGUCCACACU3'
Linc00668-MUT	5'AGGUGACAUCACAUUUGACAGAGGAAGUUACAAAGGUUAUC AACGCCUCGUCUAGUCUAUUCCCAAGAAGGACAGACAACGAAG UUCAAAGUAAGAGAGAAAUUUGUUUGUUCCAACCGAAGGUA CCAAGGAAGAAUUUCUUAACAACUUGGUGUGUGAAGUCUAAGU AAUACACAAGCACCUUGGGGUCCCUUUCGACUACAUUUUUGGAG GAAAAAAGAGGGUAUACAGAGUUUUUCAACAUAAAAGACCCA GGUCCCUAGACGUUCGGAGGAUUUCCGUAAAAGGUAACAGUGA UGGUGGUCCACACU3'
Slug-WT	5'CAATTTATGCAATAAGACCTATTCAACTTTTTCTGGGCTGGCCA AACATAAGCAGCTGCACTGCGATGCCCAGTCTAGAAAATCTTTC AGCTGTAAATACTGTGACAAGGAATATGTGAGCCTGGGCGCCCT GAAGATGCATATTCGGACCCACACAATTACCTTGTGTTTGCAAGAT CTGCGGCAAGGCGTTTTCCAGACCCTGGTTGCTTCAAGGACACAT TAGAACTCACACGGGGGAGAAGCCTTTTTCTTGCCCTCACTGCAA CAGAGCATTTCAGACAGGTCAAATCTGAGGGCTCATCTG3'
Slug-MUT	5'CAATTTATGCAATAAGACCTATTCAACTTTTTCTGGGCTGGCCA AACATAAGCAGCTGCACTGCGATGCCCAGTCTAGAAAATCTTTC AGCTGTAAATACTGTGACAAGGAATATGTGAGCCTGGGCGCCCT GAAGATGCATATTCGGACGGUGUGUATTACCTTGTGTTTGCAAGA TCTGCGGCAAGGCGTTTTCCAGACCCTGGTTGCTTCAAGGACACA TTAGAACTCACACGGGGGAGAAGCCTTTTTCTTGCCCTCACTGCA ACAGAGCATTTCAGACAGGTCAAATCTGAGGGCTCATCTG3'